

INTROVERT /EXTROVERT PERSONALITY TRAIT AND ITS EFFECTS ON MENOPAUSE CRISES

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Abstract: There is a difference on menopause crises for different women based on whether they are introverted or extraverted. This study examined the influence of extraversion versus introversion personality traits on menopause crisis for public primary schools' female teachers in Laikipia County. The study utilized ex post facto research design because it was not possible or acceptable to manipulate the characteristics of human participants. The study was based on the Big Five theory of personality. The target populations were 600 female teachers, 50 teacher counselors, 5 Sub County Directors of Education in the Ministry of Education, giving a total of 655 respondents in Laikipia County. The researcher used stratified sampling, two stage clustered sampling, random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. The sample of the study was 289 respondents. The statistical analysis entailed the computation of frequencies and percentages. The Findings revealed that extraversion versus introversion personality trait have a statistically significant influence on menopause crisis with a Linear Regression analysis where by ($r^2=0.603$; $p>0.048$) which was significant at 0.05 level of confidence. From the findings of the study, it can be concluded that extraversion versus introversion personality trait influence menopause crisis. It is recommended that counselors should aim at helping menopausal female teachers deal with their emotional instability.

Keywords: extrovert, introvert, personality traits, menopause crisis, big five theory of personality.

1. INTRODUCTION

Extraversion and Introversion describe the various attitudes individuals refer to project their energy. In psychology the meaning of the two words is different from the way they are referred in everyday language. While extravert individuals mainly tap their energy from external stimuli, such as personal interaction, social gatherings and shared ideas, introverts will find social interaction and gatherings uncomfortable and are best think clearly information and think creatively in a private setting (Difference.com, 2016; Grover, 2016; Delvis, 2014). Individuals on high levels on extraversion tend to find comfort in social situations, are outgoing, express themselves as they receive attention even from people they don't know. Most psychologists are of the view that the need for social stimulation is what drives extraverts' behaviour. Lowly extraverted individuals are regarded as introverts and characteristically more comfortable socializing in small groups and with familiar people. To them demanding social gatherings are draining and are reluctant to draw attention to themselves when in groups (Psychologist World, 2018). At the workplace, extraverted workers may be more inclined to enjoy tasks involving teamwork, working with others, or public speaking while introverts prefer working solo in reserved settings even while in meetings (Difference.com, 2016). In addition, while extraverts often thrive on collaboration, introverts prefer to find out what their specific tasks are and accomplish them alone. Elsewhere, while introverts, more often prefer to work on one task at a time, extraverts often enjoy the challenge of several projects. Introverts may also find it challenging in an environment with too many distractions, while extraverts may have difficult working in isolation (Delvis, 2014). Though hereditary factors have been shown to influence personality trait, research has equally suggested a significant role of environmental factors in personality development. Furthermore, studies have revealed a connection between subjective

well-being and extraversion that even when alone, extraverts are happier than introverts (Psychologist World, 2018). A study by Lauriola and Iani (2015) revealed that there is a good relationship between extraversion and most measures of well-being in both younger and older individuals. In addition, lower levels of extraversion (that is introversion) are associated with depression among all stages of menopausal women (Wieder-Husla, et al 2014). Extraverts get their energy from interacting with others, while introverts get their energy from within themselves. Extraversion includes the traits of energetic, talkative and assertive. High extraversion is often perceived as attention-seeking and domineering. Low extraversion causes a reserved, reflective personality, which can be perceived as aloof or self-absorbed (Toegel & Barsoux, 2012). Introverts lack the exuberance, energy and activity levels of extraverts. They tend to be quiet, low-key, and deliberate and disengaged from the social world.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study utilized *ex post facto* correlational research design. *Ex- post facto* research can be viewed as experimental research in reverse. *Ex post facto* research is ideal for conducting social research when is not possible or acceptable to manipulate the characteristics of human participants. It is a substitute for true experimental research and can be used to test hypotheses about cause and effect or correlational relationships, where it is not practical or ethical to apply a true experimental or even a quasi-experimental design (Simon & Goes, 2013). The research design was appropriate for this study since the independent variables were not be manipulated to establish their effects on the dependent variables. The research design was adopted in order to determine the influence of the independent variables under study that is neurotic personality related characteristics and female teacher's menopause crises (the dependent variable). A structured questionnaire was used to gather raw data from the female teachers in public primary schools in the study area. The questionnaire comprised items on the female teachers' extrovert versus introvert personality trait in relation to menopause crises.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

Results of descriptive analysis of data on introverted versus extroverted personality traits is presented in the following section. The respondents were guided by a Linkert scale in which 1 represented Strongly Disagree (SD), 2 represented Disagree (D), 3 represented Neutral (N), 4 represented Agree (A) and 5 represented Strongly Agree (SA).

The researcher obtained and analysed data on extrovert versus introvert personality trait and presented it in Table 1

Table 1: Descriptive Results on Extraversion Personality Trait

CODE	Statements	1=SD	2=D	3=N	4=A	5=SA
E1	I warm up quickly to others	5.7% (12)	16.7% (35)	18.2% (38)	45.0% (94)	14.4% (30)
E2	I laugh a lot	10.0% (21)	29.7% (62)	23.0% (48)	23.9% (50)	13.4% (28)
E3	I reveal little about myself	11.0% (23)	12.4% (26)	13.4% (28)	44.5% (93)	18.7% (39)
E4	I am not a very enthusiastic person	19.6% (41)	30.6% (64)	24.9% (52)	18.2% (38)	6.7% (14)
E5	I take charge	2.9% (6)	11.5% (24)	16.3% (34)	44.0% (92)	25.4% (53)
E6	I can talk others into doing things	8.6% (18)	13.4% (28)	10.5% (22)	49.3% (103)	18.2% (38)
E7	I hold back my opinions	16.7% (35)	42.1% (88)	17.2% (36)	18.2% (38)	5.7% (12)

The results posted in table 1 reveal that female teachers agreed on all the items. All the items except three had over half agreeing on the statements. The items were 'I laugh a lot' had 37.3% agreeing and 23% were neutral. In her article, Afridi, (2017) notes that laughter brings one closer to people, moves one into more positive mind-sets, can stimulate the immune system, enhance learning and memory and help coping better with the stressors in people's lives. However, in some instances it has been reported to be harmful and thus controlled laughter might be more appropriate (Benwell, 2019). 'I am not an enthusiastic person' findings revealed that 24.9% agreed while 24.9% were neutral. Afridi, (2017) proffers that

the absence of positive thoughts has a greater negative impact on health and well-being than does the presence of negative ones and that women undergoing menopause should cultivate positive thoughts and emotions. According to Dargan (2017), women undergoing menopause often lack the spark, energy and vitality to carry out their obligations and in addition, it is relevant to avail support to women going through menopause in view of helping them in getting vibrant and resourceful again. The statement that 'I hold back my opinions' 23.9% agreed while 17.2% were not sure. Fang (2007) proffers that open communication will foster effective decision making as well as enhance transparency which will in turn promote trust. Additionally, it will enhance efficient collaboration that promotes synergy and integrated workflows that make it easy to build value.

A majority, (59.4%) agreed that they warm up quickly to others while 18.2% were neutral. This corroborates with the findings of Afridi (2017) that Social interactions with family and community, nurturing relationship and healthy emotional support from friends are very effective means of coping with menopausal symptoms. Afridi, (2017) also postulates that menopause is a period in life characteristic of a drop in the physiological processes of the body and may lead to psychosocial alterations in form of interpersonal relationships.

Further, the findings revealed that 63.2% of the respondents agreed that they reveal little about themselves while 13.4% were not sure. This means that at menopause, female teachers reveal little about their self and this is contrary to the findings of Aarti, (2011) that social support is key to health and can even help one live longer. This is one of the first pieces of advice women share. Aarti further states that during menopause, women need other women with a rich life experience and wisdom to share.

Majority, (69.4%) agreed that they take charge. This serves as a backup that at menopause, primary school female teachers do take charge. In a report by the Fang (2007) there was a relationship between the menopausal symptoms and employee performance and that the severity of the menopausal symptoms may lead to a drop-in engagement at the work place as well as compromised job satisfaction. This may in return propagate a higher intention to quit work. The respondents agreed that they talk to others into doing things (67.5 %) while 10.5% were not sure. These findings are an implication that public primary school female teachers undergoing menopause can talk others into doing things. It further suggests a relatively stable emotional and mental outlook of the female teachers.

Table 2: Female Teachers' Means on Influence of Extraversion on Menopause Crisis

CODE	Statements	Mean	SD
E1	I warm up quickly to others	3.45	1.105
E2	I laugh a lot	3.01	1.217
E3	I reveal little about myself	3.47	1.241
E4	I am not a very enthusiastic person	2.62	1.184
E5	I take charge	3.78	1.043
E6	I can talk others into doing things	3.55	1.184
E7	I hold back my opinions	2.54	1.139

The seven items in table 2 on extraversion personality trait to menopause were measured using Likert scale of 1 to 5 where the lowest 1 represented strongly Disagree and the highest 5 represented Strongly Agree. A mean of 2.5 to 5.0 represented high influence while a mean of less than 2.5 meant less influence. The seven items indicate that the means ranged from 2.54 (SD=1.139) to 3.78 (SD=1.0413). Most of the means were above 2.5 meaning that majority of the respondents agreed with the statements. The SD were high as per the statements 1.043 to 1.241 which is an indication that there was a high variation of the responses to the items. These findings collaborate with Fang (2007) whose study revealed that the lower levels of extraversion are associated with depression among all stages of menopausal women which is a psychological effect of menopause.

The relationship between extraversion and menopause crises show a strong relationship as indicated by ($r^2=0.603$; $p>0.048$) which was significant at 0.05. The findings revealed a significant difference between extraversion and menopause crises. These findings are consistent with Lauriola and Ian (2015) who found a positive relationship between extraversion and most measures of well-being in the younger and older individuals.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings showed that there was statistically significant difference between female teachers' personality characteristics and menopause crisis ($r^2=0.603$; $p>0.048$) at 0.05 confidence level. Therefore, the null hypothesis that stated that 'there is no statistically significant difference between personality traits and management of menopause crises among female teachers in public primary schools in Laikipia County' was rejected. Majority were of the view that their personality characteristics influenced how they managed the menopause crises.

5. CONCLUSION

Extrovert versus introvert personality traits have a statistically significant influence on menopause crisis. Female teachers in menopause transition should understand their personality characteristics so that they can understand themselves and cope with stresses brought by menopause symptoms.

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